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Impact of Social-Support-Technique on Management of Separation-Anxiety among Student-Victims of Armed Banditry in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated impact of social support technique on management of separation-anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The study was guided by two objectives which were transformed in to hypotheses. The study employed pre-test post-test quasi experimental research design with the population of 15 student-victims who exhibited separation anxiety as identified using Spence Anxiety Scale, (1994). A sample of 10 student-victims with higher symptoms was used. The instrument used for data collection was an adapted Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder. It has a total of 20 items measuring physical and behavioural components of separation anxiety. The instrument was measured on five Point-Likert scale with a reliability coefficient of .763. Data collected were on pre-test, treatment sessions and post-test respectively. The results of the study revealed that social support technique has significant effect in managing physical symptoms of separation anxiety $p = .000$. similarly, social support technique has significant effect in managing behavioural symptoms of separation anxiety $p = .000$. Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that social support technique has significant effect in managing physical and behavioral symptoms of separation anxiety. It was recommended that Government should employ experts with adequate training in the use of social support technique in the schools to assist students how to deal with separation anxiety problems and teachers should be sensitized how to observe separation anxiety symptoms and invite experts for treatment interventions.

Keywords: Social Support Technique, Separation Anxiety, Armed Banditry

Introduction

The armed banditry movement is not a new phenomenon in Zamfara state because it had historical antecedents since the pre-colonial period, when communities around Kwatarkwashi, Mada, Tsafe, and Dan-sadau were accused of being associated and collaborating with the crime actors. The hills of Kwatarkwashi and Tsafe for instance, provided shelter to the perpetrators, from where they organized and executed their unwholesome activities in the past which made the criminals untraceable, but nowadays it is easier for security personnel to discover and arrest the armed banditry actors at diversified rural communities across the state and inter-state forest more especially in the North-western Nigeria. Some traditional rulers around the Dan-sadau area were accused of colluding with bandits in armed robbery and cattle rustling around 1891 (Rufa'I, 2021). At that material time, the situation was beyond traditional rulers exclusively, the accusation comprehends top politicians, security personnel, strong businessmen and women in the rural areas, okada riders, even religious leaders, and multitudinous peoples are involved in armed banditry affairs.

Armed banditry attacks across Zamfara, Sokoto, Kebbi, Katsina, Kaduna, and some parts of Niger state are beyond human imagination due to the failure/inactiveness of the federal and states government to protect the lives and properties of their people. There are unidentifiable reasons why federal government top officials are not willing to take action against armed banditry actors, this unwillingness leads to unmeasurable attacks on various communities and even local government headquarters across the north-western states. This situation influences individuals to migrate from their communities to the Gusau metropolis, some are moving to a peaceful part of Niger state for farming activities mentioned issues are amenable for migrating to the Gusau metropolis, considering Gusau as a capital city of the state with manageable security challenges, Student-victims of armed banditry find themselves in a new environment, associated with unfamiliar people within and outside the school environment, this might be a factor responsible for separation anxiety challenge among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Anxiety is an emotion characterized by an unpleasant state of inner turmoil, often accompanied by nervous behavior such as somatic complaints and ruminations. It is the subjectively unpleasant feelings of dread over anticipated events, such as

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the feeling of imminent death. Anxiety is a feeling of uneasiness and worry, usually generalized and unfocused as an overreaction to a situation that is only subjectively seen as menacing. It is often accompanied by muscular tension, restlessness, fatigue and problems in concentration. However, anxiety can be appropriate, but when experienced regularly it may be a disorder (APA, 2013). Every individual has feelings of anxiety at some point in their life, anxiety affects their behavior and thoughts on a daily basis, interfering with their academic performance and interpersonal relationship with classmate, friends and community members. Freud (2006) viewed anxiety as the symptomatic expressions of the inner emotional conflict caused when a person suppressed (from conscious awareness) experiences, feelings or impulses that are too threatening or disturbing to live with. Anxiety has many forms, but for the purpose of this research separation anxiety is the concern of the researcher to investigated.

Separation anxiety is a natural part of the developmental process unlike separation anxiety disorder, normal separation anxiety indicates healthy advancements in child's cognitive maturation and should not be considered a developing behavioural problem (Redlich, 2015). Separation anxiety is one of the psychological problems that is different from general anxiety disorder, although it can be difficult to pinpoint the difference because symptoms can overlap. Separation anxiety occurs after stressful life event or in a situations perceived as uncontrollable or unavoidable like armed banditry attacks. Separation anxiety refers to exhibition of excessive fear and persistent worry as a results of detachment from significant people especially parents, siblings, peer group, community members as a result of armed banditry attacks. Separation anxiety disorder is one of the most common childhood anxiety disorders (Vaughan, Caddington, Ahmed & Ertel, 2017).

Separation anxiety problems probably are the most common psychopathology in youth, with prevalence estimates ranging from 5% to 25% worldwide, but a much lower percentage receive treatment (Boyd Kostanski & Gullone, 2000; Castello, 2003). Separation anxiety disorders accounts for approximately half of the referrals among all anxiety disorders (Cartwright-Hatton, McNicol, & Doubleday, 2006). Most pediatric anxiety disorders have some diagnostic criteria as those in adults except separation anxiety disorder, currently classified in DSM and ICD as one of the disorders usually diagnosed in infancy, childhood, or adolescence (Krain, Ghaffari, & Freeman, 2007). Separation anxiety disorders has been described as a gateway anxiety disorder that can lead to variety of poor mental and physical health outcomes (Battaglia, 2015).

Social support technique is a psychological and counseling technique, which use to helps individuals to generate solutions to a problem or problems. It is particularly useful when an individual want to break out of an established pattern of thinking and decision-making, so that such individual can develop new ways of looking at things, foster and enhance communication skills. Social support is a psychological technique that helps individuals to overcome issues that can make group problem-solving a sterile and unsatisfactory process. Social support is often used in a generic sense to describe groups who generate ideas. Moran, Talbot and Benson (1990) defined social support technique as "a group process in which group members collectively contribute their 'ideas in a creative atmosphere'" Although the term has come into popular use, facilitators should know its precise meaning and history. Social support technique combines a relaxed, informal approach to problem-solving with lateral thinking. It asks that people come up with ideas and thoughts that can at first seem to be a bit crazy. The main concept in social support technique is that some of the ideas generated can be drafted into original, creative solutions to the problem that an individual trying to solve, while others can spark still more ideas.

Social support technique is understood as the help provided by individuals who comprise the social network of a person who occupies the position of ego in this network. A distinction is made between perceived and received support, as well as between psychological /emotional support on one hand and instrumental support on the other. Social support technique, therefore, is the functional dimension of the social network, which is not limited to a collection of egocentric ties that vary in number, intensity and frequency of contacts, but may be broadened to include the wider context of the community as a network of networks and to social capital, understood as the possible benefits both for individuals and groups resulting from mutual cooperation and collaboration (Angel, Natalla, Susan, & Santiago, 2016).

The social learning theory was proposed by Bandura. The works of Ewen in Ford Martins, (2014) have contributed to our understanding of the social learning theory. The social learning theory proposed by Bandura has become perhaps the most influential theory of learning and development. While rooted in many basic concept of traditional learning theory. Bandura believed that direct reinforcement could not account for all types of learning. Thus, Bandura was quoted to have said that: "Learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous at people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do fortunately, most human behaviour is learned observationally through modeling from observing others, one forms an idea of how new behaviours are performed and on later occasions, this coded information serves as a guide for action". Asonibare (2014) has stated that modeling, imitation, observational learning or social learning is used by various experts interchangeably to refer to the same thing. The therapist who is to treat separation anxiety and other

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psychological disorders is, by this concept, to present a high degree of prestige, competence, warmth, confidence and positive regard for the clients. Bandura has stated that the following steps are involved in social learning and modeling process: Attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation (Carbonel, 2014). Bandura social learning theory play a vital role in social support technique

Beck cognitive theory of anxiety was developed mainly to help individuals develop more realistic and rational appraisals of themselves and the situations they encounter. Beck is focused on the way the anxious people think about situations and potential dangers. They submitted that individuals who suffer from generalized anxiety tend to make unrealistic appraisals of certain situations, primarily those in which the possibility of danger is remote. They also argued that the Student-victims of separation anxiety burden themselves with task irrelevant cognitions. This kind of mental tasks makes a person hyper vigilant, always on the lookout for signs of danger. Cognitive theorists like Ellis and Beck as cited in Ossai (2013), stressed the role of maladaptive thought patterns and beliefs. Among the most important cognitive distortion according to Ossai (2013), are tendencies to exaggerate the amount of threat in the environment and to underestimate one's resources or ability to cope with situation demands. This is consistent with Tobia as cited in Ossai (2013), as they believed that it is not events or problems, which cause separation anxiety but rather it is the individuals' interpretation of these events that may lead to these problems. Beck theory of anxiety is significant in this study as they traced why armed banditry developed anxiety and the manifestation of physical and behavioral symptoms.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives of this study were to determine:

1. The effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.
2. The effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Methodology

This research employed pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design in investigating the effect of social support technique in managing separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. Pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design was used to determine the efficacy of the technique in managing separation anxiety symptoms by comparing pretest and post-test mean scores after exposure to the treatment. If pre-test and post-test scores differ significantly, then the difference may be attributed to the independent variable (Colman, 2015). The population of the study comprises Student-victims of armed banditry identified at Government Girls Day Secondary School, Tudun-wada Gusau with separation anxiety problems, with total population of fifteen (15) Student-victims. However, the target population stood at ten (10) Student-victims who were identified with high separation anxiety using Separation Anxiety Checklist Instrument by Spence (1994). Therefore, a sample of ten (10) participants is appropriate for quasi-experimental research as justified by De-winter (2013) who suggested that, the sample size is dependent on the nature, risk, cost and prevalence of the research conditions, a sample of 3-40 can be used in experiment. Also, better results are achieved in a smaller group and there would be effective concentration and understanding of the treatment by the participants. Based on the predicting of the researcher, Student-victims with mild and moderate separation anxiety symptoms did not require much of psychological intervention while student-victims with severe symptoms may require medical professional attention. Therefore, Student-victims of armed banditry with high separation anxiety symptoms were considered for this study.

Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder Instrument were adapted and utilized from Grasko, Wittchen, Bogels, Steinandrew and Lebeu (2013) and Spence Anxiety Scale were also adapted from Spence (1994). Severity Measure for Separation Anxiety Disorder Instrument covers a wide range of physical and behavioural symptoms of separation anxiety. It consists of 20 Items. Items 1-10 measuring physical component, items 11-20 measuring behavioural component. The instrument was designed on five-point Likert Scale ranging from Never, Occasionally, Half of the time, Most of the time, to

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All of the time. This indicates levels of separation anxiety and Spence Children Anxiety Scale was used to identifying Student-victims with high separation anxiety problems. The research instrument has a reliability coefficient of .763, while the componential analysis of the instrument revealed that physical component has the reliability coefficient of .746 and behavioural component has the reliability coefficient of .846. Therefore, the adapted instrument was reliable to measure separation anxiety. The data collected were subjected to statistical analyses using descriptive and inferential statistics. Paired sample t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Table 1: Paired Sample t-test of Pre and Post-Tests of Social support technique in Managing Physical Component of Separation Anxiety

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Pretest	10	42.80	4.39	9.81	9	.000
Posttest	10	24.40	2.01			

Table 1 revealed significant effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis as indicated by mean of 42.80 for pre-test and the mean of 24.40 for post-test; $t = 9.81$ and $p = .000$ which is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores physical component of separation anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis.

Table 2: Paired Sample t-test of Pre and Post-Tests of Social support technique in Managing Behavioural Component of Separation Anxiety

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p
Pretest	10	37.00	3.49	14.73	9	.000
Posttest	10	20.70	1.76			

Table 2 shows significant effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis as vindicated by the mean of 37.00 for pre-test and the mean of 20.70 for post-test; $t = 14.73$ and $p = .000$ which is lower than 0.05 alpha level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference pre-test and post-test mean scores of behavioural components of separation anxiety among student-victims of armed banditry exposed to social support technique in Gusau metropolis is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result of this study revealed significant effect of social support technique in managing physical component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The finding is backed up by Bello (2021) who investigated the effect of social support techniques on depression among HIV/AIDS-infected women in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Three objectives and three corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Hypotheses formulated for the study were statistically analyzed using a paired-sample t-test. Results of the data analyzed for the study showed that cognitive restructuring and social support techniques are both effective in reducing depression, which showed both techniques have an effect in reducing depression among HIV/AIDS-infected women ($p = 124$). The finding is also in line with the study of Sirati-Nir, Khaghanizade, Rahimi, Khazaei and Ghadirian (2018) who investigated the effect of social support technique-training group intervention on perceived social support technique in veterans with posttraumatic stress disorder. Traumatic events related to war have long effects on psychiatric psychopathologies. The ANOVA results showed that after the intervention, there were significant differences in perceived social support technique between intervention groups and control group ($F = 1.06$, $P = 0.001$), but there was no significant difference between intervention groups by t-test ($t = 28.05$, $p < 0.10$). The paired t-test showed a significant difference in all subscale scores of perceived social support technique between the two intervention groups

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before and after intervention ($p < 0.05$). The results of the current study agreed with the positive effects of social support technique training on perceived social support technique in veterans with post-traumatic stress disorder.

The finding of the study showed significant effect of social support technique in managing behavioural component of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis. The findings were in consonance with the study of Maulik, Eaton, and Bradshaw (2011) examines the moderate effect of social support on the relationship between stress and depression of university students. A total of 632 undergraduate students completed the measures of perceived stress, perceived social support, and depression. The results of these analyses are presented. Stress ($B = 0.44$, $P < 0.01$) significantly presented depression in the second step. The social support factor added a significant increment to the model in step three, where social support ($B = -0.30$, $p < 0.01$) was significantly related to depression after controlling other variables. Moreover, a significant interaction between stress and social support ($B = -0.10$, $P < 0.01$) was present, as predicted. The findings suggested that social support moderated the impact of stress on depression. Significantly positive relationship exists between stress and depression at low levels of social support ($B = 0.47$, $p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.22$). The relationship between stress and depression was significant at high levels of social support ($B = 0.22$, $p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.04$). The regression coefficient, however, was significantly less than that in the low social support group. Hence, the results also suggest that social support moderated the impact of stress on depression.

Conclusion

It was concluded that social support technique was significantly effective in managing physical and behavioural components of separation anxiety among Student-victims of armed banditry in Gusau metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study it was recommended that:

1. Government should employ experts with adequate training in the use of social support technique in the schools to assist students how to deal with separation anxiety problems and teachers should be sensitized how to observe separation anxiety symptoms among their Student and invite (experts) psychologists and counsellors for intervention.
2. Non-Governmental organizations should collaborate with federal and state governments to support teachers and IDPS camps officials to manage separation anxiety disorders with goals of promoting better mental health which lead to higher academic performance and achievements among student-victims of armed banditry.

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